

Future Circular Collider

REPORT

MARKET RESEARCH OF DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS FOR THE FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER PROJECT

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1. MOTIVATION

To manage the Future Circular Collider (FCC) project, a systemic approach to managing documents is required. The complexity of the project arises from its organisational, structural, physical and technological aspects, and from the diverse nature of the project documentation and the stakeholders who need to make use of it.

There is a critical need for a solution that can ensure efficient, secure, and accessible documentation workflows inside and outside CERN with contracted organisations and collaboration partners worldwide. Experience of the concept and feasibility studies between 2014 and 2024 shows that the management of the documentation is already challenging today, and the next stages of the project will bring an increase in quantity and complexity of documents and in terms of stakeholders.

The solutions available at CERN today (e.g. SharePoint, Twiki, CERNbox, OneDrive, Google Drive) are not document management solutions. CERN's Engineering Data Management Service (EDMS) provides only basic document management functions and lacks fundamental document management features such as a scalable permission management concept, on-line editing, automated information ingestion and processing, configurable views, consistent access management, automated version management (new versions are not automatically created after modifying the document), file system integration, intuitive search and filtering mechanisms, full-text search result presentation, user-programmable workflows, and dispatching mechanisms and most of all, suitable functionality to work with individuals, companies and organisations outside CERN.

2. REQUIREMENTS OVERVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The requirements for a Document Management System (DMS) were gathered via several interviews with stakeholders in the FCC feasibility study.

The revealed required functionalities were divided into the following categories:

- Document structure
- Unique identification
- Document access
- Search & filter
- Metadata customization
- User-centric views
- Workflow management
- File editing
- Document conversion
- Access & authentication
- Cross-platform access
- Revision management
- User roles
- Hosting scenarios
- Automated tagging
- Document summary
- Total cost of ownership
- Integration with email systems
- Automated ingestion and processing

Some of the functionalities were deemed as “must-haves”, which simplified the initial solution identification process. If a solution did not fulfil one or more of the “must-have” requirements, it was disqualified, and the further investigation of this solution was stopped. The list of all must have functionalities is presented in chapter 7¹.

Costing is based on a simplified approach assuming license costs for 50 named users, or 10 concurrent users (whichever was cheaper), deployment and configuration costs, and maintenance costs over 5 years. The pricing provided by the companies does not include migration from legacy services and should be treated as an estimate.

To be able to compare solutions amongst those fulfilling the criteria, weights were added to the parameters and functionality score was calculated. Having that, a general rank was calculated using the VIKOR method which considered prices and functionality scores of the qualified solutions.

The detailed breakdown of the functionalities, must-have requirements, and their comparative analysis is accessible in the DMS comparison Excel table that is associated with this report.²

¹ Chapter 7 of the present report: Annex

² <https://zenodo.org/api/records/10809821/draft/files/FCC-2310191007-MZI-DMSMarketResearchExcelComparison-V0100.xlsx/content>

3. POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

The potential solutions can be divided into the following categories:

- Used at CERN
- Used in similar organizations
- Used in commercial companies and public authorities

The information about those solutions was obtained by interviews with users, administrators, DMS consultants, DMS producers, 3rd party implementation companies, and self-research of the publicly available information.

The following 31 solutions were analysed and are presented in this report (Table 3-1). The three most promising solutions are highlighted on the table below.

Solution (Ordered by VIKOR-based ranking algorithm)	Suitable	Available at CERN	VIKOR Rank
OpenKM	Yes	No	1
M-files	Yes	Partially	2
Docuware	Yes	No	3
Therefore	Yes	No	4
Alfresco	Yes	No	5
Laserfiche	Yes	No	6
Eclipse	Yes	No	7
Aras Innovator PLM	Partially	Yes	8
Disqualified solutions			
Agile e6 PLM based Engineering and Equipment Data Management System (EDMS)	No	Yes	
CERNBox	No	Yes	
MS SharePoint	No	Limited	
Infor IDM	No	Limited	On-premises version will be discontinued in April 2024
OneDrive	No	Limited	
GoogleDrive	No	Limited	
ITER DMS	No	No	

Confluence	No	No	
Techdoc	No	No	Discontinued
Lucidoc	No	No	Discontinued
Mayan	No	No	
IManage	No	No	
Paperless NGX	No	No	
Teedy	No	No	
Aodocs	No	No	
Nuexo	No	No	
Hyland onBase	No	No	
Dokmee	No	No	
Piqnic	No	No	
Oracle Documaker	N/A	No	Discontinued
Xerox Docushare	N/A	No	
NetDocuments	No	No	
Iguana	N/A	No	

Table 3-1. Potential DMS solutions analysed.

First, the 23 disqualified solutions will be presented, with a note describing the reason(s) to not further consider the solution as a potential general DMS for the project.

3.1. USED AT CERN - DISQUALIFIED

3.1.1. Engineering and Equipment Data Management Service (EDMS)

1. Lack of collaborative functions: EDMS is a sophisticated PLM system with a primary focus on engineering and equipment data management. It lacks the necessary project document management functions across organization boundaries. While “Collaborative editing” (not necessarily "concurrent editing") could be counterproductive for engineering use cases, it is essential for project management. This specialization means it might not be ideally suited to handle the broader range of document types and workflows anticipated for the FCC project.
2. Extra steps required from users: lack of "in tool" editing or "office suite integrated editing" could also hinder efforts of having a sole source of truth, as EDMS requires reupload of documents, and often users omit this step and keep files on which they work on their personal drives. This approach also hinders a methodological approach for revision management.
3. Potential for UX improvements: based on the experiences of the EDMS users in the FCC team, EDMS provides a different user experience compared to contemporary solutions, which provide aesthetically pleasing interface, simpler navigation and more intuitive operation. This might prevent the adoption of EDMS as a solution for all project relevant documents.
4. Access limitations: FCC works with many stakeholders outside CERN. Many of them will not be willing to create and update the CERN NICE and lightweight accounts, which are required to access EDMS documents.
5. Search functionality: while a full text search exists, it is not intuitive to use and does not report the matched text directly. There exists no reporting of the results in a form that permits understanding where in documents the searched elements were found.
6. User centric views: diverse stakeholders in a project require different views and organisation structure of the same underlying document set. EDMS does not provide this functionality.
7. Inconsistent access mechanism: the "context" based access mechanism leads to inconsistent accesses across document hierarchies and a challenging access management task. While the access management is configurable, it must be carefully planned, and a simple access overview is not available out of the box.
8. Permission management mechanism: it is not easily scalable and does not help to make understandable what is accessible and what not, who has access to what and what not.
9. Public documents: the only way to share a document in EDMS with someone without a CERN account, is to make it public. This is not ideal, as anyone will be able to find a document.
10. Revision management: documents are "nodes" that can contain multiple files, but revision management is manual and does not scale to large amounts of concurrent versions, because it requires creating a new version of a node, which is a time consuming process.

3.1.2. CERNBox

1. Designed for cloud file storage: CERNBox is a cloud storage and file-sharing service. While it facilitates basic document sharing and collaboration, it lacks the document management functionalities entirely.
2. The search function is not working: currently most of the feasibility study documents are in CERNBox and they cannot be easily found based on their title, authors, metadata, and content. Additionally, CERNbox does not attribute unique IDs to files, which makes the search less systematic.

3. File system occupation: CERNBox is not a network file system, but a cloud storage system that synchronises files to the local file system, thus filling up the local computer disk. However, effective search in the file system is only possible if the files are locally synchronised. This also leads every now and then to issues with concurrent write access across computers and native file systems. Additionally, the synchronisation itself is not always working properly.
4. Folder structure: structuring of the documents is done using folders, which quickly gets too complex to navigate. Multiple views are not possible. File system links that could be used to create different views are not supported by CERNBox.
5. Information scalability: to scale with the information needed to be managed, CERNBox requires the creation of additional file shares. This makes the entire information management process complicated to manage in terms of location of the information and access to users.
6. Limited access management: access is based on propagating permissions from the root node to the leaves. This approach is contrary to common file system access approaches that permit restricting access to individual subfolders or even preventing the visibility of subfolders. CERNBox does not implement such functionality.
7. The product bug and feature request cycles are extremely long, typically in the order of months and years even for basic fixes and improvements. This makes the solution unsuitable for the management of project documentation.
8. FCC is currently using CERNbox to manage most of the project documents, but its operation has been described as unsatisfactory by several project members, because of the following problems³:
 - Local disk space consumption
 - Unintended overwrites
 - Inconsistent file locking
 - Absence of logical links and misuse due to lack of knowledge
 - Loss of link control
 - Creation of links on project shared not possible
 - Absence of permanent links that can be programmatically generated (or at least strong limitations to create permanent links programmatically)
 - Difficulty to manage permissions
 - Limited performance from outside CERN
 - Limitation of file system size due to single management account
 - Problematic authenticated access for non-CERN registered persons
 - Integration with web services is outdated or at least not regularly maintained
 - Very limited search functionality

3.1.3. Microsoft SharePoint

1. Based on experience with SharePoint in the FCC study between 2014 and 2018, the solution does not qualify as a specialized Document Management System: SharePoint is primarily a collaboration platform. While it offers document storage and basic management features, it lacks several advanced features needed for the project.

³ https://cernbox.cern.ch/files/spaces/eos/project/f/fccproject/office/IT/file%20system%20needs/FCC-210628_FileSystemNeeds4FCCStudy.docx

2. Customization challenges: customizing SharePoint to meet the document management needs of the project would be challenging and resource-intensive both initially and during the usage period. Server-side access would be needed and cannot be granted at CERN. Client-side programming is extremely limited and strongly version dependent. Using SharePoint would require hiring SharePoint developers and consultants.
3. Labour intensive tagging: SharePoint does not support automatic tagging based on the content of the documents.
4. Limited user centric view configurability: views would need to be coded using tables and filters. While in principle this is possible, end users will find it difficult without advanced training to create their own document views based on selection criteria.
5. Risk of data loss: SharePoint online used at CERN is hosted on Microsoft servers. In case of contract rupture data stored there might be lost. Additionally, occasionally the existing SharePoint online service at CERN is not working. In that case, there is no possibility to access or recover documents that are stored there, disqualifying SharePoint to manage project critical documents.

3.1.4. OneDrive & Google Drive

1. Cloud storage systems exhibit the same issues as CERNBox and cannot be considered a DMS.
2. Cloud solution only: as in the case of SharePoint, cloud solutions are not suitable for project critical documents.
3. Lack of advanced document management features: OneDrive and Google Drive are not document management systems and they lack its basic functions as workflow management.

3.1.5. Infor Document Management (IDM)

1. The on-premises version will be discontinued: Infor Document Management (IDM) was rolled out at CERN in January 2024. It is hosted on CERN premises and is integrated with other CERN systems. It fulfils basic requirements of a DMS, but, unfortunately, the on-premises version will be discontinued and from April 2024 Infor will offer only cloud-based solutions. FCC cannot use the on-premises version as the software will be left without support and development by the supplier.

3.2. USED IN SIMILAR ORGANIZATIONS – DISQUALIFIED

3.2.1. ITER DMS - ITER

1. Lack of in-system file editing: in 2005 ITER introduced a new DMS based on “ZOPE” and later rebuilt it using “.Net”⁴. ITER DMS does not include in-system editing capabilities and it is folder based, which limits the flexibility of setting up the views and entails the necessity of creating “shortcuts” between documents in different folders to avoid duplication.

⁴ https://inis.iaea.org/collection/NCLCollectionStore/_Public/36/043/36043459.pdf?r=1

3.2.2. Confluence – NASA

1. Too many customizations: Confluence would require significant effort from the CERN side to make it work as a DMS, as many functions, such as for instance document approval, are not present in basic Confluence.^{5,6}

3.2.3. Techdoc - NASA

1. Discontinued: aside from Confluence, NASA also uses Techdoc to browse their documents – but the latest update of this software is from 2019, which suggests that they have abandoned the project.

3.2.4. Lucidoc - NASA

1. Discontinued: Lucidoc was developed by NASA as a DMS, but it seems to have been abandoned as well.⁷

3.3. USED BY COMPANIES AND PUBLIC AUTHORITIES - DISQUALIFIED

3.3.1. Mayan

1. Lacks in-system editing capabilities: Mayan is the only fully open-source DMS project that was found during the research (there were others that featured community editions with limited capabilities). Because Mayan is open source, it does not have a connector with Microsoft Office, which is required to be able to edit the documents directly in the system. Except for this, it fulfils other required functions, and having a longer timescale and more workforce it could have been an interesting solution.

3.3.2. IManage

1. Lacks workflow management.
2. It is a cloud only solution.

3.3.3. Paperless NGX

1. Lack of document versioning.

3.3.4. Teedy

1. Allows one level tag-based hierarchies only: no possibility of having "folders" or "workspaces". This limits the possibility of hierarchical organization of documents. Tag-based only hierarchy is not sufficient for the project's use cases.

3.3.5. Aodocs

1. Cloud only: Aodocs integrates with Google workspace adding document management capabilities. It would be an interesting option to leverage Google workspace already used at CERN, but it would stay a cloud only solution. In addition, it would lock the project into the Google suite.

⁵ https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/ivv_05_document_control_ver_an_03-10-2020.pdf

⁶ <https://www.atlassian.com/customers/nasa>

⁷ https://spinoff.nasa.gov/Spinoff2005/ct_4.html

3.3.6. Nuexo and Hyland onBase

1. Limited workflow management capabilities: Nuexo and Hyland onBase are owned by the same company (the later presented Alfresco as well). Based on the shared requirements and use cases, the Hyland representative advised Alfresco as the best solution among the three available, especially in terms of developed workflow management.

3.3.7. Dokmee

1. No in-system office documents editing so far.

3.3.8. Piqnic

1. No in-system office documents editing.
2. No tree view for folders.

3.3.9. Oracle Documaker

1. The further development of the solution has been suspended. Oracle does not have other alternatives for DMS.

3.3.10. Xerox docushare

1. No response from the company: Xerox never replied after multiple contact attempts. DMS consultants discouraged using Xerox due to signs of the solution being retired.

3.3.11. NetDocuments

1. Cloud version focus: although the solution could be deployed on premise, login would still go through the supplier portal, which disqualifies the solution because it would make us dependent on the supplier. NetDocuments is created mostly for use in the legal industry.

3.3.12. Iguana

1. No response from the company regarding detailed functionalities: based on the information from their website, Iguana has most of the required functionalities, but it was not possible to discuss more advanced functionalities with the company. While gathering information on Iguana, the company's website behaved not consistently. Furthermore, it has an outdated user interface.

4. SOLUTIONS FULFILLING ALL MUST-HAVE REQUIREMENTS

There are no solutions that are currently being used at CERN and that fulfil the must-have criteria.

The solutions that fulfil those criteria and are recommended for further consideration can be divided into the following categories:

- Currently being rolled out at CERN.
- Free version of the software is used at CERN.
- Used at the European Space Agency (ESA).
- Used in commercial companies and by public organisations elsewhere.

4.1. CURRENTLY BEING ROLLED OUT AT CERN

4.1.1. M-Files

1. *M-files* is a metadata-based DMS that permits the creation of arbitrary views and document bundles.
2. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *M-files* in the second place out of eight qualified solutions.
3. *M-files*, as of January 2024, is being rolled out for use in the CERN Pension Fund only.
4. The company doing the implementation – Neuronex – is based in Geneva.

4.2. FREE VERSION OF THE SOFTWARE IS USED AT CERN

4.2.1. Aras Innovator

1. *Aras Innovator* is a Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) tool, which includes capabilities of a DMS.
2. Like EDMS currently used at CERN it imposes a rigid document organisation, targeted at linking documentation to elements of a product breakdown structure. While suitable for engineering documentation, this may be a limitation for less structured project management documentation.
3. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *Aras Innovator* on the eighth place out of eight qualified solutions.
4. CERN EN Information Management Group deployed a free version of Aras which in the future aims to replace EDMS. Currently it is mostly used for CAD files. It can be accessed via the following link: plm.cern.ch.
5. The free version used at CERN does not have all the functionalities required for the FCC DMS. For instance, it lacks full text search and in-system editing, but the team responsible for implementation is open to discussion regarding potential functionalities in the future.

4.3. USED AT ESA

4.3.1. Eclipse

1. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *Eclipse* in the seventh place out of eight qualified solutions.
2. was chosen in 2015 to upgrade their *POLARIS* document management system.⁸
3. *Eclipse* is a Document Management System based on Oracle, tailored to the space industry.
4. Based on an exchange with ESA, the ESA directorate has started efforts to streamline digital tools to replace the customized *Eclipse* with Microsoft suite products (*Teams*, *OneDrive*, *SharePoint* online) and with the Teamcenter PLM made by Siemens. ESA plans to use Microsoft DMS products for project management and collaborative documents, and Teamcenter PLM for product-oriented documents. Their next challenge is to set clear boundaries on exactly what documents should be saved in each of the systems.

4.4. USED IN COMMERCIAL COMPANIES AND PUBLIC ORGANISATIONS

4.4.1. Therefore by Canon

1. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *Therefore* on the fourth place out of eight qualified solutions.
2. Canon is already a CERN supplier - irisXtract is used to extract data from financial documents.
3. Their Swiss headquarters are in Carouge.

4.4.2. Laserfiche

1. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *Laserfiche* in the sixth place out of eight qualified solutions.

4.4.3. Alfresco

1. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *Alfresco* in the fifth place out of eight qualified solutions.
2. *Alfresco* is the most expensive tool among the qualifying ones (600 kCHF).

4.4.4. Docuware

1. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *Docuware* in the third place out of eight qualified solutions.

⁸ <https://www.eclipsesuite.com/sapienza-consulting-awarded-a-contract-for-the-provision-of-polaris-esa-corporate-services/>

4.4.5. OpenKM

1. Functionalities and price weighted average score put *OpenKM* in the first place out of eight qualified solutions.
2. *OpenKM* has also a free community edition, which has limited capabilities.
3. Although *OpenKM* fulfilled all the functionalities and represents the cheapest deployment scenario (15 kCHF), the subjective perceived user experience of the system during the demo was not the best among the qualifying tools. However, the web interface of the solution is modern and would be worth investigating in a case study.

4.5. SUMMARY OF QUALIFIED SOLUTIONS

The research provided the following findings:

1. There are solutions in the market that are better suited to the FCC DMS needs than what is currently used at CERN.
2. The solution that fulfilled all the must-have and nice-to-have functionalities and provided the lowest price estimation is *OpenKM*. *OpenKM* was ranked first using the VIKOR comparison.
3. Two of the qualified solutions, *M-files* and *Aras Innovator* are being deployed at CERN: *M-files* in the Pension Fund, and *Aras Innovator* as a CERN-wide PLM tool, with the plan to replace eventually EDMS. *Aras Innovator* is, however, strongly linked to engineering documentation, potentially leading to similar limitations as EDMS. *M-files* was ranked onsecond out of eight and *Aras Innovator* was ranked eighth .
4. Other solutions that qualify as DMS candidates for the project listed in order of their VIKOR rank are:
 - a. *Docuware*
 - b. *Therefore*
 - c. *Alfresco*
 - d. *Laserfiche*
5. *Eclipse* was an initially qualified solution. Since during an interview with ESA personnel *Eclipse* was described as unsatisfactory and they explained that is has been decided to implement Microsoft Suite and Teamcenter PLM, *Eclipse* should not be considered as a candidate solution for FCC.

5. FURTHER CONSIDERATIONS

5.1. SOLUTIONS ALREADY USED AT CERN

The two solutions currently being deployed at CERN are *M-files* and *Aras Innovator* as PLM. Using them can significantly decrease the lead time of getting a DMS for FCC. Implementing a solution not already in use at CERN necessitates considering several factors, requiring additional time, money, and efforts:

1. Time and effort involved in the procurement process.
2. Time, effort, and budget required for the technical implementation.
3. Time and effort needed for Computer Security and Data Privacy validation.
4. Time and effort to obtain approval from IT for introducing new software at CERN.
5. Resistance for adoption by several departments and groups using other tools.

5.2. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PLM AND DMS SOLUTIONS

Since the two solutions already being implemented at CERN are Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) system and Document Management System (DMS), a general comparison of those types of solutions was carried out.

5.2.1. Product Lifecycle Management Systems (PLM)

PLMs are particularly suitable for product development projects. Their strengths include:

1. Centralized information management: They create a single source of truth for all project aspects, including technical and management documents.
2. Lifecycle tracking: PLMs are effective in capturing the entire product lifecycle, beneficial for intricate development and maintenance phases.
3. Collaboration and integration: PLM systems often facilitate better the close integration of data and information from engineering teams and integrate well with various engineering and project management tools, enhancing overall project efficiency. They rely, however, on a well-defined product structure.

5.2.2. Document Management Systems (DMS)

DMS solutions are more focused on document-centric tasks and are ideal for projects requiring efficient document management in less structured environments. Their advantages are:

1. User-friendly interface: DMS systems are more user-friendly, encouraging higher adoption rates, especially in less technical areas of a project.
2. Streamlined document management: They offer a straightforward approach to document handling and storage, without the complexity of broader functionalities.
3. Flexibility and customization: DMS solutions often provide greater flexibility in terms of customization to meet specific project needs, making them adaptable to a variety of document management scenarios.

5.2.3. Simultaneous use of DMS and PLM systems

Because of how different the DMS and PLM systems are, many organizations decide to simultaneously use both systems, as it is the case for ESA. ESA decided to use the Teamcenter PLM system for engineering documents, and an array of Microsoft solutions based around SharePoint for project management and

collaborative documents. This approach has the benefit of using tools better suited for the nature of work but creates a risk of data duplication between the systems if their boundaries are not clearly defined.

5.2.4. Exclusive use of a PLM system

Using exclusively a PLM system to manage all documents for all use cases in an organisation, while showing a promise of a single source of truth, comes with a risk of lower adoption of the tool among the employees. The setup of EDMS at CERN shows this situation. While it could be used to manage documents, many teams at CERN never use it due to the additional effort required when managing the documents there, which resulted in scattered documents among many systems and private drives. A PLM is not suited to all types of documentation, in particular it is not the most suitable approach to manage project management documentation and documentation in unstructured and dynamic environments.

5.3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

5.3.1. OpenKM DMS

1. *OpenKM* is the only solution that fulfilled all must-have and nice-to-have functionalities. It is also the cheapest out of the qualifying solutions. For the first 100 users it is 50 EUR per user, for more it is 25 EUR per user. Basic installation and configuration are 20% of the licence fees.
2. *Open KM* is very feature rich, which is a positive side, but compared to more streamlined solutions, it can be overwhelming for unaccustomed users.
3. *OpenKM* is based on folders, which has less flexibility than metadata-based hierarchy but is more familiar to users accustomed to CERNbox

Figure 5-1. Selection, metadata, and preview of documents in OpenKM.

Figure 5-2. Graphical representation of the workflow process in OpenKM.

4. The basic capabilities are shown in a short, 3-minute video.⁹
5. *OpenKM* offers a free cloud trial version of the enterprise version.

5.3.2. M-FILES DMS

1. This solution was placed on the second rank by VIKOR analysis, but it fulfilled all the must-have requirements, and it is already being used at CERN.
2. Using *M-files* instead of installing another DMS will not go against the CERN document management consolidation efforts.
3. Implementation of *M-files* at CERN started in January 2024. The FCC team could test the CERN *M-files* instance as soon as it is be available.
4. A one-month trial is version of *M-files* is available for download.¹⁰
5. Cost per user license per month is 49 EUR. The standard implementation time is 50 days, and the daily rate is 1440 CHF. In the market research a time of 10 days was assumed, since it will be already implemented at the CERN Pension Fund and mostly the functional consultation will be needed.
6. *M-Files* uses the approach of classifying documents with metadata and categorizing content into metadata-based views, which gives a greater usage flexibility, but can be non-intuitive for users accustomed to folder-based views.

⁹ <https://www.openkm.com/openkm-remastered.mp4>

¹⁰ <https://www.m-files.com/product-downloads/download-update-links/>

Figure 5-3. Selection, metadata, and preview of documents in M-files.

7. M-files provides a visual workflow builder, with possibility of having multiple workflows per document.

Figure 5-4. Workflow for a document “in-work” in M-files.

Figure 5-5. Workflow for a "published" document in M-files.

5.3.3. Aras Innovator PLM

1. The paid enterprise version of *Aras Innovator* PLM meets the must-have criteria for the DMS.
2. The CERN deployed PLM is based on the free *Aras Innovator* software, which is limited in terms of the functionalities required by the project.

Figure 5-6. Dashboard of CERN PLM.

Figure 5-7. Metadata of a non-technical document in CERN PLM.

3. As the project is in the phase of development, the team responsible for the implementation is open to suggestions for new functionalities. Two examples of those functions, which are not present in the free version and required in the FCC DMS, are full text search and in-system files editing.
4. The scope and timeline of those changes is not known.

6. CONCLUSIONS

6.1. RAPID DEPLOYMENT

M-Files is today a solution which seems in principle to be able to fulfil all FCC project needs and has the potential for rapid deployment since the tool is currently being rolled out at CERN in the Pension Fund.

M-files should be tested and compared in detail with *OpenKM* in a dedicated evaluation environment. If it is confirmed that *M-Files* satisfies the needs and *OpenKM* does not provide significantly more added value, *M-Files* could be adopted.

6.2. MEDIUM TERM DEPLOYMENT

In case of planning the deployment in a longer timescale, *OpenKM* and *M-Files* should be tested and compared in detail. Both are priced similarly. A decision on which solution to adopt should be made based on their performance and considering the efforts required to deploy and maintain it.

If the *M-Files* and *OpenKM* turn out to be unsatisfactory during the test phase, the alternatives to consider and test are the following qualifying solutions in order of priority:

1. *Docuware*
2. *Therefore*
3. *Alfresco*
4. *Laserfiche*

6.3. TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

As a long-term technical documentation management system for civil engineering, particle accelerator and experiment designs, a PLM with DMS capabilities is the preferred approach.

The FCC project should work closely with the Information Management team from the Engineering Department which is in charge of the PLM solution at CERN to ensure that the CERN PLM will have the required functionalities.

However, for the purposes of project management and for the non-technical areas of the project, a Document Management System is a better fit.

As it was described in the chapters “Simultaneous use of DMS and PLM systems” and “Exclusive use of a PLM system”, a decision should be made whether CERN PLM should be used as the principal solution for managing documents, or if a DMS should be used simultaneously to it.

7. ANNEX

Table 7-1. List of requirements and must have functionalities

Requirement category	Summarized Requirement	Must-have
Document Structure	Hierarchical organization of digital assets	X
	A document can be linked to another document	X
	Multiple views for documents based on user needs	X
	A document can be referenced in many structures	X
Unique Identification	Unique, persistent identifiers for each document	X
Document Access	Direct access to documents via identifiers or URLs	X
Search & Filter by	Metadata	X
	Free text	X
	AI search through the document content	
Metadata Customization	Define and modify metadata fields per document type	X
User-Centric Views	Customizable topical and hierarchical document views	X
Workflow Management	Customizable document workflow processes	X
File Editing	In-system editing for office documents	X
	Check in, check out - 1 person at a time editing	
	Live collaborative editing	
Document Conversion	Automated conversion to formats like PDF	
Access & Authentication	Role-based access control, compatible within/outside CERN	X
	Anonymous viewers	
	Possibility to edit documents by external users	

Cross-Platform Access via different OS	Windows	
	Mac	
	iOS	
	Android	
	Web	
	Web optimized for mobile use	
Revision Management	Comprehensive tracking and management of revisions	X
User Roles	Different user permissions and management roles	X
Hosting Options	On premise	X
	Cloud	
Automatic tagging based on	File content (keywords etc.)	
	AI interpreted file content	
	Metadata	
Automatic summary	AI generated file content summary	
Outlook integration	Saving emails as documents	
Scan ingestion	Documents from scanner being sent to the system	